

ENGLISH IS THE LANGUAGE OF OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract. Nowadays, attention to language learning is increasing. The demand and interest in learning foreign languages, especially English, has increased so much that children from kindergarten to senior professionals are trying to learn English. Why do we need this language? We will try to reveal the mistakes in learning this language and what doors are opened by learning this language in the life of our hero Shavkat.

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Why do we need to learn a new language? What opportunities does learning a new language give us? In today's article, we are looking for an answer to this.

Today, the most popular language, which is becoming a world language, is English. What are the advantages of this language? First, English is the most widely spoken language in the world. Learning English will help you get a job in the fields of science, aviation, computers, diplomacy, and tourism. Secondly, learning English helps to meet new people. It is the official language of 53 countries of the world. Many scientific works are written in English. It is much easier to travel if you know English well. Think about it, if you are an Uzbek citizen on vacation in Miami, the administrator of your hotel may not be able to answer your question in Uzbek, but he can answer your question in English. English provides access to several cultures. A good command of the English language allows you to access films, music and literature from hundreds of countries around the world. Not to mention that many books around the world have been translated into English. About 2,000,000,000 people in the world speak English. Another 1,000,000,000 are learning this language. This language is the mother tongue of approximately 400,000,000 people in the world. In approximately 60 of the 196 countries of the world, English is accepted as the main language. It can be seen from these that English is becoming one of the most developing languages. What should we pay attention to when learning this language? Our hero Shavkat started learning this language in the 3rd grade. But he himself did not understand why he should learn it. He attended extra classes only because his parents forced him. He did not do the tasks of the class, he went to a new teacher every two or three months. Years later, he entered the lyceum. Then he began to understand that this language is necessary. This language is needed in IT, tourism, and legal fields. Knowing this language alone would make 90% of all computer functions familiar. After that, he started attending additional classes, but unfortunately his level was very low. In addition to going to courses 3 days a week, he also studied separately. With the help of the Internet, he made new friends and conducted conversations with them. It was very difficult at first, he did not know many words. Completed 6 parts of Essential English Words. As soon as he started the new part, the old one started to leave his mind. Now he began to get positive results after memorizing the vocabulary by the backward method. When he was young, he used to write down the words that he could not read next to the stories in simple English, similar to the stories that his mother had read. He found the meanings and synonyms of some words and wrote them next to the stories. In the beginning, he had a lot of trouble, he was looking for many words in dictionaries. This situation changed when reading stories became continuous. The most important rule in

language learning is continuity and continuity. Now gradually the words he did not know in stories and books began to decrease. In addition, he studied the English language and the grammar of his mother tongue with passion. His teacher told him: First of all, a person should know his mother tongue well, a person who does not know his own language well cannot learn another language better than. He also started watching movies in English to improve his listening and comprehension skills. Shavkat loved watching movies from a young age. Watched movies with subtitles, which was more effective than regular viewing. The best TV series and movies I reviewed in English were the following.

1. "Friends"
2. "Remember the Titanic"
3. "How I met your mother"
4. "Harry Potter" (all parts)
5. "Pirates of the Caribbean"
6. "Sherlock Holmes"
7. "The Freedom Writers"

At the time when our hero was studying so well, he started to feel bad for some reason. Various pains in his body increased. He went to the doctor, and after a long examination, he was told that he had not one, but several tumors, which could be a sign of cancer. Surgery was performed in two parts of his body. Analysis results came out in a week. Thank God, this is a tumor that appears as a result of hormonal disorders. It took 6 months for Shavkat to come to his senses. But during this time he studied while sitting in the room, even if he did not go to extra classes. He loved history, so he listened to historical events and podcasts in English. The more a person learns a new language, the more his thinking expands. Shavkat's goals are now much wider. Two years of hard work paid off and he got 8.5 in the English language exam. Now he devoted all his attention to studying history. When he entered the lyceum, good teachers helped him to learn this subject in depth. He applied to the Faculty of Law of the University of Law, entered the state university with 189 points, and became the recipient of the Presidential Diploma. Parents were called to the school and thanked for raising a wonderful child. Now our hero is studying at Stanford University in California, USA. This hero of ours exists in real life, and there are many people who are working on it.

Facts about the English language show that it is very important today. For a person, learning another language will help you make new friends, boost your self-confidence, and make your ministry more meaningful.

I would also like to add that a good mood, positive inner mental experience and good rest are also very important in learning a foreign language. Tony Robbins says, "Even the best methods and rules account for only 20 percent of success. The other 80 percent depends on human psychology." According to experts, maintaining and forming a positive mental experience is more powerful than the methods used in language learning.[]

We saw mistakes in language learning in the life of our hero Shavkat and made a conclusion. We also listed the effective methods he used. Learning one language opened the doors of the world for him. Now he can take his parents on trips around the world. It can easily show that the earth is infinite, that there are new life and cultures in other places.

You will have difficulty in learning English at the beginning, you cannot learn this language just by going to a 1.5-hour class 3 days a week. Nothing is learned so easily. You will be

with the teacher for 1.5 hours, and the rest of the day you will be on your own for 22.5 hours. Improve the environment, create an environment where conversations about the English language take place. Read more YouTube, podcasts, blogs, because most of the blogs in your field are interesting and in English. Every 2 weeks, 1 month, summarize your results and write about the changes. This is a method that can provide the main motivation for your next actions. You too, my dear friend, should start learning your favorite language right now, but don't give yourself too many tasks and let it cool off. You can develop your speaking, listening and reading skills through ChatGPT, which is developed on the Internet. You and I live in an age of opportunity. We just need to use it properly.

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